

NANOFACTS

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1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of dissemination and communication activities during the past 27 months of the NANOFACTS project, with a specific focus on the period from March 2022 to June 2024. We have continued our collaboration with our partners, Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Ireland, The School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, and Vienna University of Technology (TUW), Faculty of Technical Chemistry, Institute of Applied Synthetic Chemistry and Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics, to implement the most effective dissemination strategies.

As the conditions of the COVID-19 outbreak improved, we were able to shift back to a more balanced approach between virtual and in-person communication and dissemination activities. While maintaining a robust online presence, we resumed organizing face-to-face meetings and events, ensuring adherence to any remaining health and safety guidelines.

Online Dissemination Activities

To maintain and expand our online presence, we continued to focus on our Website and social media platforms. These channels were crucial in reaching a broad audience, including the scientific community, industry stakeholders, and the general public. We regularly updated our website with project news, publications, and event announcements. Our social media strategy included frequent posts, engagement with followers, and targeted campaigns to increase visibility and reach.

In-Person Dissemination Activities

With the easing of COVID-19 restrictions, we were able to organize and participate in several in-person events. These included conferences, workshops, and seminars where we presented the progress and findings of the NANOFACTS project. A significant event was the Training School, which took place in July 2022, attracting a diverse group of participants and facilitating valuable knowledge exchange.

Target Groups and Tailor-Made Messages

We continued to craft tailor-made messages to effectively reach and engage our target groups:

Scientific Community: We disseminated our research findings through peer-reviewed publications, conference presentations, and collaborative projects.

Industry (Pharmaceutical Companies): *We discussed with industry representatives at conference events and organized meetings to highlight the potential applications of our research in pharmaceutical development.*

Potential Users (Patients): Information to patients was conveyed through media interviews, our website and social networks.

Students: We promoted specialization in nanotechnology and cancer research through academic workshops, and participation in our Training School.

General Public: We provided updates on the latest cancer research developments through public lectures, media interviews, our website and social networks.

Dissemination Events

Our dissemination activities included a mix of virtual and in-person events:

- **Website Traffic:** Our website continued to be a primary source of information, with increased traffic due to regular updates and targeted Search Engine Optimization, SEO strategies.
- **Social Media Activity:** Engagement on social media platforms remained high, with strategic content creation and interaction with followers.
- **Scientific Publications:** We published several articles in high-impact journals, contributing to the scientific discourse on nanotechnology and cancer research.

- Conferences and Workshops: We attended and organized various national and European events, facilitating direct interaction with peers and stakeholders.
- In this report, the following segments are presented in detail: website traffic, social media activity, scientific publications, as well as dissemination events attended or organized by BIOS staff, engaging national and European community.

The implementation of this dissemination overview provides a detailed description of the main dissemination activities. The news about the NANOFACTS project was spread through the official web portal, social media platforms, face-to-face meetings, and dissemination events. This report covers the dissemination activities for the second reporting period from March 2022 to June 2024.

2. Report on Dissemination Tools and Activities

Table 1: Overview of NANOFACTS dissemination activities

Period M16-M42 value	Period M01-M16 value	Activity	
53458	15 470	Number of unique views of NANOFACTS website	Overall
10	5	Number of news published by NANOFACTS website	
43	19	Unique post published on all NANOFACTS social media accounts	
544	364	Followers on social media	
9	3	Conference publications	
...	7	Dissemination events	
4	2	Internal face-to-face meetings	
17	5	News published on NANOFACTS website in English	NANOFACTS website
45	19	Tweets posted on NANOFACTS twitter profile in English	Twitter account
41	21	Followers on twitter	
43	19	Posts published on NANOFACTS Facebook page in English	Facebook page
155	146	Facebook page likes	
173	156	Page followers	
43	19	Posts published on Instagram page	Instagram account
156	90	Followers on Instagram	

174	91	Followers on LinkedIn account	LinkedIn account
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2.1. Electronic dissemination

2.1.1. The website

The **NANOFACTS** website serves as the primary source of information about the project's goals, stages, events, and team members. It is designed to provide a comprehensive overview of the project, with detailed sections on individual work packages, key personnel, and illustrations representing the project's activities. The website, accessible at www.nanofacts.net, aims to clearly present the **NANOFACTS** concept and approach. Additionally, it functions as a platform for disseminating project results, showcasing **NANOFACTS** publications, and highlighting other scientific achievements.

Figure 1. New page dedicated to Training School added to the website

Figure 2. New page dedicated to Training School added to the website

Figure 3. The website statistics – January 1st 2022 to December 31st 2022.

Figure 4. The website statistics – January 1st 2023 to December 31st 2023.

Figure 5. The website statistics – January 1st 2024 to June 30th 2024.

Figure 6. The website visitors' locations - January 1st 2022 to December 31st 2022

Figure 7. The website visitors' locations - January 1st 2023 to December 31st 2023.

Locales (Top 25) - Full list				
Locales		Pages	Hits	Bandwidth
United States	us	3,804	7,683	544.60 MB
Republic of Serbia	rs	1,894	13,187	764.82 MB
China	cn	923	1,838	187.61 MB
Russian Federation	ru	300	662	143.69 MB
Netherlands	nl	270	480	17.18 MB
Canada	ca	236	358	26.94 MB
Austria	at	235	1,847	93.61 MB
Germany	de	232	831	55.56 MB
Great Britain	gb	217	930	42.56 MB
India	in	210	1,389	68.07 MB
Romania	ro	98	142	13.91 MB
Spain	es	89	703	41.99 MB
France	fr	83	177	13.73 MB
Iran	ir	80	80	11.64 MB
Sweden	se	61	91	5.35 MB
Poland	pl	47	137	10.10 MB
Portugal	pt	42	275	11.43 MB
Ireland	ie	42	547	47.21 MB
Vietnam	vn	39	40	2.97 MB
Seychelles	sc	38	39	3.21 MB
Bulgaria	bg	37	45	2.71 MB
Switzerland	ch	36	122	8.25 MB
Czech Republic	cz	35	283	27.93 MB
Ukraine	ua	25	27	3.20 MB
Greece	gr	25	209	7.88 MB
Others		523	2704	144.06 MB

Figure 8. The website visitors' locations - January 1st 2024 to June 30th 2024.

2.1.2. Facebook page

The **NANOFACTS** project maintains its own Facebook page, which is also regularly promoted through the BioSense Institute's Facebook page. The **NANOFACTS** Facebook page is frequently updated with the latest results, news, and achievements of the **NANOFACTS** researchers.

Figure 9. Facebook photos posted in the period April 01st 2022 – June 30th 2024.

Figure 10. Facebook posts with highest interaction rate - April 01st 2022 - June 1st 2024.

Figure 11. Facebook account - Audience statistics

Figure 12. NANOFACTS project dissemination through BioSense Institute Facebook page and Facebook page of the Faculty of Technology in Novi Sad, Serbia

2.1.3. Instagram page

The **NANOFACTS** project's Instagram account continues to maintain a notable presence within the academic social media sphere, particularly targeting a younger audience. Its primary purpose is to showcase the ongoing activities of the researchers involved in the project. Regular updates on the account highlight the latest results, news, and achievements of the **NANOFACTS** researchers, thereby maintaining the project's visibility and recognition within the nanotechnology community.

Figure 13. NANOFACTS Instagram account

Figure 14. NANOFACTS Instagram posts in period June 2022 - June 2024

Figure 15. Instagram posts with highest number of impressions – Posts related to NANOFACTS Training School and Secondment Related stories

Figure 16. Instagram stories with highest number of impressions – NANOFACTS Training School and Secondment related posts

2.1.4. LinkedIn account

Through the **NANOFACTS** LinkedIn account, we aimed to reach the academic and industrial population, with a particular focus on the research community. Our goal was achieved, as demonstrated in Figure 18. which displays follower demographics. The posts that received the most interactions were related to our workshops, secondments, and paper publications.

Figure 17. NANOFACTS LinkedIn account

Figure 18. NANOFACTS LinkedIn Account – Visitor Demographics

Figure 19. NANOFACTS LinkedIn Account – Followers Demographics

Figure 20. NANOFACTS LinkedIn Account – Top posts statistics

Figure 21. NANOFACTS project dissemination through BioSense Institute and other LinkedIn accounts

2.1.5. X account (previous Twitter account)

Figure 22. NANOFACTS page on X social network

Figure 23. NANOFACTS high impact posts on X social network – related to Training School

Figure 24. NANOFACTS high impact posts on X social network – related to Scientific publications

Figure 25. NANOFACTS activities through BioSense X account

2.2. Printed dissemination

Scientific publishing is a key channel for reaching academia, researchers, and professionals within the project's scope. NANOFACTS researchers have disseminated their results through open-access, peer-reviewed international journals and presentations at international conferences. Below is the list of scientific publications published in the period from March 2022 - June 2024:

2.2.1. Scientific journal publications

1. Nekrasov, N.; Kudriavtseva, A.; Orlov, A.V.; Gadjanski, I.; Nikitin, P.I.; Bobrinetskiy, I.; Knežević, N.Ž. One-Step Photochemical Immobilization of Aptamer on Graphene for Label-Free Detection of NT-proBNP. *Biosensors* 2022, 12, 1071. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios12121071>
2. Knežević, N.Ž.; Ilić, N.; Kaluđerović, G.N. Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for pH-Responsive Delivery of Iridium Metallotherapeutics and Treatment of Glioblastoma Multiforme. *Inorganics* 2022, 10, 250. <https://doi.org/10.3390/inorganics10120250>
3. Erthal, L. C., Shi, Y., Sweeney, K. J., Gobbo, O. L., & Ruiz-Hernandez, E. (2023). Nanocomposite formulation for a sustained release of free drug and drug-loaded responsive nanoparticles: an approach for a local therapy of glioblastoma multiforme. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 5094.
4. Ultimo, A., Orzaez, M., Santos-Martinez, M. J., Martínez-Máñez, R., Marcos, M. D., Sancenón, F., & Ruiz-Hernández, E. (2023). High-capacity mesoporous silica nanocarriers of siRNA for applications in retinal delivery. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(3), 2753. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24032753>
5. Maher, R., Moreno-Borrillo, A., Jindal, D., Mai, B. T., Ruiz-Hernandez, E., & Harkin, A. (2023). Intranasal Polymeric and Lipid-Based Nanocarriers for CNS Drug Delivery. *Pharmaceutics*, 15(3), 746. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15030746>
6. de la Torre, C., Coll, C., Ultimo, A., Sancenón, F., Martínez-Máñez, R., & Ruiz-Hernández, E. (2023). In Situ-Forming Gels Loaded with Stimuli-Responsive Gated Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Local Sustained Drug Delivery. *Pharmaceutics*, 15(4), 1071. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15041071>

7. Spitz, S., Schobesberger, S., Brandauer, K., Ertl P. (2023). Sensor-integrated brain-on-a-chip platforms: Improving the predictive validity in neurodegenerative research. *Bioengineering & Translational Medicine*. doi:10.1002/btm2.10604
8. Jarić, S., Schobesberger, S., Velicki, L., Milovančev, A., Nikolić, N., Ertl, P., Bobrinetskiy, I., Knežević, N. (2024). Direct electrochemical reduction of graphene oxide thin film for aptamer-based selective and highly sensitive detection of matrix metalloproteinase 2. *Talanta* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2024.126079>
9. Kudriavtseva, A.; Jarić, S.; Nekrasov, N.; Orlov, A.V.; Gadjanski, I.; Bobrinetskiy, I.; Nikitin, P.I.; Knežević, N. (2024) Comparative Study of Field-Effect Transistors Based on Graphene Oxide and CVD Graphene in Highly Sensitive NT-proBNP Aptasensors. *Biosensors* 2024, 14, 215. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios14050215>
10. Mundžić, M., Lazović, J., Mladenović, M., Pavlović, A., Ultimo, A., Gobbo, O.L., Ruiz-Hernandez, E., Santos-Martinez, M.J., Knežević, N.Ž. (2024). MRI-based sensing of pH-responsive content release from mesoporous silica nanoparticles. *J Sol-Gel Sci Technol*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10971-024-06422-9>
11. Mladenović, M., Jarić, S., Mundžić, M., Pavlović, A., Bobrinetskiy, I., Knežević, N.Ž. Biosensors for Cancer Biomarkers based on Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles (2024), *Biosensors*, 14(7), 326; <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios14070326>

2.2.2. Preprint publications

1. Mundžić, M., Ultimo, A., Lazović, J., Mladenović M, Pavlović A, Gobbo O, Ruiz-Hernandez E, Santos-Martinez MJ, Knežević N.Ž. pH-responsive Nanosystems for Targeted Drug Delivery to Glioblastoma Multiforme and MRI-facilitated Monitoring of Content Release, 11 December 2023, PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square [<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3709910/v1>]
2. Kundacina, I., Schobesberger, S. Kittler, S., Thumfart, H., Spadiut, O., Ertl, P, Knezevic, N.Ž. Radonic, V., A Versatile Gold Leaf Immunosensor with a Novel Functionalization Strategy Based on Protein L-Modified Surface for Efficient Her2 Detection. 2024, PREPRINT Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4740306> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4740306>

2.2.3. Conference publications

1. N. Ž. Knežević, N. Ilić, G. N. Kaluđerović, Functionalized Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Drug Delivery to Glioblastoma, Multiforme, 22nd IEEE International Conference on Nanotechnology (IEEE-NANO 2022): Book of Abstracts, 4-8 July 2022, Palma de Mallorca, Spain
2. A. Pavlović, M. Mladenović, M. Mundžić, Nanosensor for the detection of glutathione , 15th Scientific Conference Students encountering science – StES 2022, 17-19 November 2022, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
3. T. Knežić, M. Djisalov, LAMP PRIMER DESIGN FOR MONITORING GENE EXPRESSION OF TUMOR MARKERS IN 3D CANCER CULTURES , 15th Scientific Conference Students encountering science – StES 2022, 17-19 November 2022, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
4. Nikola Knežević, Minja Mladenović, Mirjana Mundžić, Aleksandra Pavlović, Mila Djisalov, Teodora Knežić, & Ivana Gadjanski. (2023, February 9). Cyclodextrin-Capped Mesoporous Silica-Based Nanomaterials for pH-Responsive Targeted Theranostics of Glioblastoma

- Multiforme. International meet on pharmaceuticals and drug delivery systems (PHARMAMEET2023), Porto, Portugal.
5. N. Ž. Knežević, M. Mundžić, M. Mladenović, A. Pavlović, A. Ultimo, O. L. Gobbo, E. Ruiz-Hernandez, M. Santos-Martinez. pH- and Redox-Responsive Cancer Nanotheranostics Based on Cyclodextrin-Capped Mesoporous Silica. 20th International Conference on Nanosciences & Nanotechnologies, Abstract book, P97, July 4-7, 2023, Thessaloniki, Greece
 6. Stefan Jarić, Silvia Schobesberger, Peter Ertl, Nikola Knežević, Ivan Bobrinetskiy. Electrochemical detection of MMP-2 using graphene based aptasensor'' XXXV EUROSENSORS, 10-13 September 2023, Lecce, Italy, <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2024097057>
 7. Jarić, S., Schobesberger, S., Bobrinetskiy, I., Knežević, N. Utilizing the high sensitivity toward MMP-2 of an electrochemically reduced graphene oxide aptasensor, in Proceedings of the 4th International Electronic Conference on Biosensors, MDPI: Basel, Switzerland
 8. Jarić, S., Bobrinetskiy I., Low-cost platform for determination of NTproBNP in saliva using graphene-based aptasensor. 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology, 12-15 May, 2024. Seville, Spain
 9. Knežević, N., Jarić, S., Kundačina, I., Radonić, V., Bobrinetskiy, I. Novel cost-effective electrochemical systems for sensing cancer biomarkers, Rapid Communication, 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology, 12-15 May, Seville, Spain
 10. Knežević, N.Ž., Mundžić, M., Lazović, J., Ultimo, A., Mladenović, M., Pavlović, A., Gobbo, O.L., Ruiz-Hernandez, E., Santos-Martinez. M.J. Potential of MRI-based sensing of cargo release from mesoporous silica for tracking drug delivery capabilities. NanoSpain, June 04-07, 2024. Tarragona, Spain.

2.3. Dissemination events

2.3.1. Training School

Announcement and marketing

The **NANOFACTS** Training School "Training School in Nanoparticles, their application in cancer treatment, imaging and sensing" held in Novi Sad from 27th June- 1st July, was a pivotal event aimed at harnessing nanotechnology in medicine. Over the course of five days, participant delved into innovative approaches to address the limitations of conventional cancer therapies and propel the development of personalized diagnostic and therapeutic tools. Esteemed international experts led sessions tailored for Ph.D. students, researchers, and young professionals, fostering a dynamic exchange of knowledge. Topics spanned from cutting-edge biosensors for cancer detection to the design of nanomaterials for targeted therapy and imaging. Additionally, the curriculum explored clinical and surgical aspects of cancer treatment, offering insights into emerging cancer biomarkers. Beyond scientific content, the training underscored the importance of foundational research skills such as creative thinking, teamwork, and problem-solving. Participants also benefited from sessions focused on writing scientific project proposals, project implementation, and startup management, aimed at fostering researchers' self-sustainability.

Figure 26. Leaflet with general information about Training School

The organization of Training School started months ahead, inviting speakers, preparing agenda and organizing marketing strategies. To provide official information and for easier application, a new page on the **NANOFACTS** website titled “Training School” has been added. This page was used to provide related information about Training School as well as the application form and agenda.

Figure 27. Training School page on Website with detailed information

A new section on the website “Training School” has been added containing related information as well as the application form.

The screenshot displays the nanofacts website interface. At the top, the navigation menu includes: HOME PAGE, ABOUT US, PARTICIPANTS, NEWS, TRAINING SCHOOL (highlighted), PUBLICATIONS, and CONTACT. The main content area features an application form titled "APPLY:" with the following fields:

- Your name
- Your email
- Position (occupation)
- Reason for attending (optional)

A "Submit" button is located at the bottom of the form. Below the form, two Google Maps are displayed side-by-side:

- SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY PARK:** Shows the location of "Naučno-tehnološki park Novi Sad" at Pruskogorska 1, Novi Sad, with a 4.6 star rating and 77 reviews.
- BIOSENSE INSTITUTE RECTORATE BUILDING:** Shows the location of "Dr Zorana Stinčića 1, 21000, Novi Sad" near the "Prirodno-Matematički Fakultet Univerziteta U."

Figure 28. Training School page on Website and application form

In addition to our dissemination efforts, our Dissemination Manager, MSc Minja Mladenović, made appearances as a guest on Serbian television channels RTV and Novosadska TV. During these interviews, she discussed the upcoming Training School, provided insights into the project's current progress, and outlined future plans. Furthermore, our Principal Investigator, Nikola Knežević, was featured on Serbian national television, where he highlighted the significance of the first Training School focused on nanoparticles and extended an invitation to all interested individuals to participate.

Figure 29. MSc Minja Mladenović discussing NANOFACTS project and announcing the Training School on the national TV program.

Figure 30. PI Dr. Nikola Knežević discussing the First Training School on Nanoparticles in Serbia on the national TV program

Figure 31. Design for promo material for socials (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn)

Content on social media platforms was shared not only through NANOFACTS pages and channels, but also through BioSense accounts, and Faculties of University of Novi Sad, inviting students, researchers and professors to join.

Figure 32. NANOFACTS Training School announcement on all social media platforms (Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn)

Speakers and agenda

NANOFACTS team has invited 16 speakers (Figure 33.) from various eminent European institutions (Table 2) to present their work and teach workshop attendees more about the most recent studies about cancer treatment and diagnostics.

Figure 33. Training School speakers

Table 2: *Invited speakers, Institution and Country origin*

	Name	Institution	Country origin
1.	Prof. Dr. Davide Peddis	Università di Genova	Italy
2.	Prof. Dr. Giuseppe Spoto	University of Catania	Italy
3.	Dr. Igor Djan	Radiation oncologist at Clinical center of Serbia	Serbia
4.	Dr. Jelena Zinnanti	Max Planck Institute	Germany
5.	Dr. Oliviero Gobbo	Trinity College Dublin	Ireland
6.	Prof. Dr. Paulo J. P. Freitas	INESC Microsistemas e Nanotecnologias	Portugal
7.	Prof. Dr. Peter Ertl	TU Wien	Austria
8.	Dr. Sanja Vranješ Đurić	Institute of Nuclear Sciences Vinča	Serbia
9.	Prof. Dr. Goran Stanojević	Faculty of Technical Sciences	Serbia
10.	Dr. Binh T. Mai	Trinity College Dublin	Ireland
11.	Prof. Dr. Nebojša Majstorović	Industrial/Organizational Psychology at the University of Novi Sad	Serbia
12.	Dr. Francesco Floris	Università degli Studi di Pavia	Italy
13.	Mr. Stavros Tsitouras	Foodscale Hub	Serbia
14.	Prof. Dr. Katarina Zeljić	Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade	Serbia
15.	Jovana Vlaškalin	BioSense Intitute	Serbia
16.	Dr. Thi Nga Tran	Trinity College Dublin	Ireland
17.	Dr. Srđan Mijatović	Specialist in urgent surgery	Serbia
18.	Dr. Nikola Knežević	BioSense Intitute	Serbia

The agenda for the **NANOFACTS** Training School and their applications in cancer treatment, imaging, and sensing is illustrated in Figure 34.

DAY 2 - TUESDAY, 28 th JUNE 2022
CANCER THERANOSTIC NANOMATERIALS
Location: Science & Technology park, UNS, Fruškogorska 1
09:30-10:25 Design of magnetic nanoarchitectures for cancer theranostics Prof. Dr. Davide Peddis
10:25-11:20 Cancer prevention using magnetic nanoparticles Dr. Oliviero Gobbo
11:20-12:15 Multifunctional nanoparticles for cancer imaging Dr. Jelena Zivanic
12:15-13:30 Lunch
13:30-14:25 Clinical aspects of cancer treatment Dr. Igor Djani
14:25-15:20 Radiolabeled nanoparticles for the application in diagnosis and cancer treatment Dr. Sanja Vranjic-Egadic
15:20-16:15 The combined use of hydrogels and nanoparticles for the treatment of brain tumors Dr. Birh T. Mal

DAY 5 - FRIDAY, 1 st JULY 2022
ONLY FOR THE NANOFACTS CONSORTIUM WORKSHOPS: CANCER THERANOSTICS
Location: Rectorate Building, UNS, Dr. Zorana Dindića 1
09:00-09:45 Nanosafety and the Regulatory Landscape (online lecture) Prof. Dr. Maria Santos-Martinez
09:45-10:30 Designing Animal Experiments Dr. Oliviero Gobbo
10:30-12:30 Workshop: In vitro assessment of therapeutic nanomaterials in 2D and 3D cell cultures, Day 2 Dr. Annela Ulbrich
12:30-14:00 Lunch
14:00-14:45 Sustainable CO ₂ -based biocomposites for active food packaging and biomedical applications Dr. Thi Nga Tran
14:45-16:45 Workshop: Preparation of composite biomaterials for biomedical application, Day 2 Dr. Thi Nga Tran

THANK YOU FOR PARTICIPATING
 WE HOPE THAT YOU HAD FUN
 LEARNING WITH US!

TRAINING SCHOOL IN NANOPARTICLES,

THEIR APPLICATION IN CANCER TREATMENT, IMAGING AND SENSING

DEADLINE FOR APPLICATION: 15th JUNE

START

Learn about cancer theranostics, cancer therapy and imaging using nanoparticles, MRI, biosensing of cancer, cancer biomarkers, microfluidic and magnetic cancer sensors, and much more in cancer-related topics

When: 27th June – 1st July 2022

Where: BioSense Institute Rectorate Building & Science & Technology Park, Novi Sad

Free participation after application on www.nanofacts.net/training-school

PARTNERS:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019719

DAY 1 - MONDAY, 27 th JUNE 2022
09:30-09:45 WELCOME ADDRESS
Location: Rectorate Building, UNS, Dr. Zorana Dindića 1
CANCER BIOSENSING AND IMAGING
09:45-10:40 NANOFACTS scientific concept: the application of mesoporous silica nanoparticles in cancer-related research Dr. Nikola Knezevic
10:40-11:35 Organ-on-a-chip applications in precision medicine Prof. Dr. Peter Ertl
11:35-12:30 Magnetic biosensing for detection of biomarkers related to cancer and other pathologies Prof. Dr. Paulo J. Pereira Freitas
12:30-14:00 Lunch
14:00-14:35 Cancer molecular biomarkers: from bench to application Prof. Dr. Katarina Zejic
14:35-15:50 Plasmonic detection of oncogenic DNA in liquid biopsy samples from colorectal cancer patients Prof. Dr. Giuseppe Spoto
15:50-16:45 Multiplexing detection of biomarkers through SPY imaging and kinetics analysis Dr. Francesco Floris

DAY 3 - WEDNESDAY, 29 th JUNE 2022
Location: Science & Technology park, UNS, Fruškogorska 1
09:30-09:45 Basic skills Training: Teamwork and creative thinking Prof. Dr. Nebojsa Majstorovic
11:00-12:00 Basic skills Training: Problem solving skills Prof. Dr. Nebojsa Majstorovic
12:00-12:15 Lunch
13:15-14:10 EU Horizon programme for funding innovative ideas in the field of biomedicine Prof. Dr. Goran Stojanovic
14:10-15:05 Guidelines for project implementation Jovana Vlahkalin
15:05-16:00 Creating and managing startups Stavros Tsiortzas

DAY 4 - THURSDAY, 30 th JUNE 2022
ONLY FOR THE NANOFACTS CONSORTIUM WORKSHOPS: CANCER BIOSENSING
Location: Rectorate Building, UNS, Dr. Zorana Dindića 1
09:00-10:00 Workshop: In vitro assessment of therapeutic nanomaterials in 2D and 3D cell cultures, Day 1 Dr. Annela Ulbrich
10:00-11:00 Workshop: Preparation of composite biomaterials for biomedical application, Day 1 Dr. Thi Nga Tran
11:00-12:00 Rapid prototyping, Workshop: Microfluidic biosensors Prof. Dr. Peter Ertl
12:00-13:30 Lunch
13:30-15:00 NANOFACTS consortium meeting
15:00-17:00 Workshop: Bio-chemical analyzer based on imaging surface plasmon resonance Eliana Munobianco and Dr. Francesco Floris

Figure 34. Design of agenda flyer for Training School

Figure 35. Design of name cards for Training school attendees and participants

Program, lectures, workshops and attendees

As mentioned, throughout the Training School, participants engaged in a multifaceted program comprising 21 lectures, 4 workshops, and a consortium meeting for **NANOFACTS** team. The following images provide a visual journey through the engaging sessions and vibrant atmosphere of the event.

Figure 36. Welcome speech from Dr. Goran Kitić, Head of Center for Sensing Technologies at BioSense

Figure 37. Welcome speech from Dr. Nikola Knežević, NANOFACTS PI

Figure 38. Lecture Presentations

Figure 39. Lecture Presentations

Figure 40. Attendees during the break

Attendee list, by each date can be seen in the following pictures:

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 27. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
1.	Miroslav Babić	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
2.	Selena Zarić	student	FTN
3.	Nina Feketić	student	FTN
4.	Nina Milešić	student	FTN
5.	Jovana Kalamboković	student	FTN
6.	Leana Milešić	student	FTN
7.	Pete Erik	visiting research	UNL
8.	Željko Blagojević	researcher	Faculty of Agriculture, Zagreb
9.	Barica Popović	researcher	-
10.	Barica Popović	vice professor	Faculty of Agriculture, Zagreb
11.	Miroslav Babić	researcher	TFNS
12.	Miroslav Babić	student	FTN
13.	Korica Vujan	student	FTN
14.	Ljiljana Babić	researcher	BIOSENSE
15.	Marija Babić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
16.	Ksenija Stanić	student	FTN
17.	Mirko Vikić	student	FTN
18.	Mirko Vikić	student	PMF
19.	Đina Zarić	student	PMF
20.	Stjepan Vlastić	Researcher	PMF NS
21.	Njira Omerović	Researcher	BioSense

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 27. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
22.	Ilda Zarić	Researcher	TFNS
23.	Dragana Jakovčić	Researcher	Virolo Institute
24.	Stjepan Blagojević	Researcher	Viro Institute
25.	MIRKA MILER	Researcher	BIOSENSE
26.	FRANJEŠKO PLOŠIĆ	Researcher	PEARSON
27.	BARICA POPOVIĆ	Researcher	PEARSON
28.	DAVINA TOGIĆ	Professor	UNL
29.	MARIJA BABIĆ	Professor	UNL
30.	Čestimir Jurić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
31.	Biljana Šarić	Researcher	Faculty of Technology, Novi Zagreb
32.	Dejvid Goble	Researcher	TCD
33.	ĐINH T. HAI	Researcher	TCD
34.	Miroslav Babić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
35.	Jana Radošević	Researcher	BIOSENSE
36.	Njira Omerović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
37.	Marija Babić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
38.	Jasna Stanić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
39.	Sara Janković	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE
40.	Čestimir Jurić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
41.	Stjepan Vlastić	Student	Faculty of Technology, Novi Zagreb
42.	Marija Babić	Student	Science Faculty
43.	Gorana Vikić	Student	Faculty of Science

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 27. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
44.	SELENA BABIĆ	STUDENT	FACULTY OF SCIENCE
45.	Barica Popović	STUDENT	FACULTY OF SCIENCE
46.	MIRKA MILER	RESEARCHER	FACULTY OF SCIENCE
47.	Stjepan Blagojević	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
48.	DAVINA TOGIĆ	PROFESSOR	UNL
49.	Čestimir Jurić	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
50.	MARIJA BABIĆ	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
51.	Mila Babić	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
52.	Pete Erik	RESEARCHER	FACULTY OF SCIENCE
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Figure 41. Attendee list, 27.6.2022.

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 28. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
1.	Nina Feketić	researcher	BIOSENSE
2.	Čestimir Jurić	junior researcher	BIOSENSE
3.	Marija Babić	Researcher	UNL
4.	Stjepan Blagojević	Researcher	BIOSENSE
5.	Marija Babić	Researcher	UNL
6.	Dejvid Goble	Researcher	TCD
7.	ĐINH T. HAI	Researcher	TCD
8.	Miroslav Babić	Student	FTN
9.	Korica Vujan	Student	FTN
10.	Marija Babić	Researcher	Faculty of Technology, UNL
11.	Đina Zarić	Student	PMF
12.	Mirko Vikić	Student	PMF
13.	Jana Radošević	Researcher	BIOSENSE
14.	Barica Popović	Senior Res.	UNL
15.	Sara Janković	Senior Res.	UNL
16.	MIRKA MILER	Researcher	BIOSENSE
17.	Barica Popović	vice professor	Faculty of Agriculture
18.	Barica Popović	researcher	Faculty of Agriculture
19.	Barica Popović	vice professor	Faculty of Agriculture
20.	Ksenija Stanić	student	Faculty of Science
21.	Jelena Kipe	student	Faculty of Science

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 28. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
22.	Pete Erik	Prof	TU VIEREN
23.	Čestimir Jurić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
24.	Marija Babić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
25.	Marija Babić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
26.	Biljana Šarić	Researcher	Faculty of Technology, Novi Zagreb
27.	FRANJEŠKO PLOŠIĆ	Researcher	PEARSON
28.	FRANJEŠKO PLOŠIĆ	Researcher	PEARSON
29.	Nina Feketić	student	FTN
30.	Selena Zarić	student	FTN
31.	Leana Milešić	student	FTN
32.	Selena Zarić	STUDENT	FACULTY OF SCIENCE
33.	Gorana Vikić	STUDENT	FACULTY OF SCIENCE
34.	Barica Popović	student	Faculty of Science
35.	Čestimir Jurić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
36.	Marija Babić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
37.	Marija Babić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
38.	Marija Babić	Student	Faculty of Science
39.	Njira Omerović	Junior researcher	BIOSENSE
40.	Sara Janković	Student	PMF
41.	Mila Babić	Junior research assistant	BIOSENSE
42.	Marija Babić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
43.	Sara Janković	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 28. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
44.	Pete Erik	RESEARCHER	FACULTY OF SCIENCE
45.	Dejvid Goble	STAFF SCIENTIST	UNL
46.	Đina Zarić	MD	Faculty of Medicine, Novi Zagreb
47.	Sanja Kojić	TEACHING ASSISTANT	Faculty of Technology, UNL
48.	Marija Babić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
49.	Miroslav Babić	STAFF SCIENTIST	BIOSENSE
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Figure 42. Attendee list, 28.6.2022.

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 29. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/ professor/other...)	Institution
1.	Edina Šiler	Teaching Assistant	University of Zagreb
2.	Uroš Pavić	PROFESSOR	VIRUM-OFIUM-BOB
3.	Marko Križanović	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
4.	Božica Džurđević	RESEARCH ASSISTANT	Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb
5.	Sara Janković	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	Biological Institute
6.	Ula Brdar	Junior Researcher	Biological Institute
7.	Miglena Nedeljković	Junior Researcher	Biological Institute
8.	Marko Križanović	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
9.	Čestimir Čičić	Researcher	University of Zagreb
10.	Nikola Jukić	Researcher	University of Zagreb
11.	Alena Jakić	Student	Faculty of Technology and Architecture, University of Zagreb
12.	Milica Pavač	student	Faculty of Sciences
13.	Željko Jukić	student	Faculty of Sciences
14.	Andrija Džurđević	student	Faculty of Sciences
15.	Božica Vid	STUDENT	Faculty of Sciences
16.	Petar ERK	Govt	TU Dura
17.	Biljana Garić	PhD student	Faculty of Technology and Architecture, University of Zagreb
18.	Dragana Pavač	Professor	University of Zagreb
19.	Uroš Pavić	Senior Researcher	BIOSENSE
20.	Edina Šiler	RESEARCHER	Faculty of Science
21.	Jelena Riga	Student	Faculty of Science

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 29. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/ professor/other...)	Institution
22.	Ksenija Dunder	Student	Faculty of Science
23.	Ilda Zlatović	Researcher	TF NS
24.	Bojan Rukavina	student	PMF
25.	Bojan Zlatović	Student	PMF
26.	Miroslav Pavač	Student	FTN
27.	Vesna Prohlević	researcher	TF NS
28.	Čestimir Čičić	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
29.	Ljiljana Pavač	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
30.	Marko Križanović	Junior Researcher	PROFENK
31.	Franciska Pavić	RESEARCHER	PLANTAR
32.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	PLANTAR
33.	Alena Jakić	JUNIOR ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
34.	MATJA KUKIČIĆ	PROFESSOR	BIOSENSE
35.	Željko Jukić	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
36.	Gođača Križanović	PROFESSOR, VES	UNIVERSITY OF ZAGREB
37.	Suzana Jukić	student	FTN
38.	Uroš Pavić	student	FTN
39.	Jelena Riga	student	FTN
40.	Miroslav Križanović	Senior Researcher	BIOSENSE
41.	Jelena Križanović	Manager	BIOSENSE
42.	Đura HAI	Researcher	TCD
43.	Ol' Gobbo	Researcher	TCD

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 29. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/ professor/other...)	Institution
44.	Jelena Jukić	Senior Researcher	BIOSENSE
45.	Ljiljana Janković	Senior Researcher	BIOSENSE
46.	Ljiljana Janković	Researcher	BIOSENSE
47.	Božica Pavač	Full professor	Faculty of Agriculture
48.	Stjepan Babić	Senior Project Manager	BIOSENSE
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Figure 43. Attendee list, 29.6.2022.

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 30. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/ professor/other...)	Institution
1.	IRENA MILER	RESEARCHER	TCD
2.	O. Gobbo	Researcher	TCD
3.	Ljiljana Pavač	Senior Researcher	BIOSENSE
4.	Miglena Nedeljković	Junior Researcher	Biological Institute
5.	Čestimir Čičić	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
6.	Alena Jakić	Junior Researcher	Biological Institute
7.	Ula Brdar	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	Biological Institute
8.	Sara Janković	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	Biological Institute
9.	Marko Križanović	Junior Researcher	Biological Institute
10.	Nikola Jukić	Researcher	University of Zagreb
11.	IRENA MILER	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
12.	Željko Jukić	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
13.	Franciska Pavić	Researcher	PLANTAR
14.	Franciska Pavić	Researcher	PLANTAR
15.	Gođača Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
16.	Jelena Križanović	Junior Researcher	Biological Institute
17.	Miglena Nedeljković	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE
18.	Čestimir Čičić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
19.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
20.	Marko Križanović	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
21.	Marko Križanović	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 30. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/ professor/other...)	Institution
22.	Jelena Jukić	Researcher	PMF
23.	Miglena Nedeljković	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE
24.	Čestimir Čičić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
25.	Ljiljana Pavač	Researcher	BIOSENSE
26.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
27.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
28.	Alena Jakić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
29.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
30.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
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Figure 44. Attendee list, 30.6.2022.

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 1. 7. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/ professor/other...)	Institution
1.	Marko Križanović	Student	Faculty of Technology and Architecture, University of Zagreb
2.	IRENA MILER	RESEARCHER	TCD
3.	O. Gobbo	Researcher	TCD
4.	Čestimir Čičić	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
5.	Ljiljana Pavač	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
6.	Miglena Nedeljković	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE
7.	Ula Brdar	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE
8.	Bojan Rukavina	Researcher	BIOSENSE
9.	Čestimir Čičić	Researcher	BIOSENSE
10.	Miglena Nedeljković	Researcher	BIOSENSE
11.	Uroš Pavić	Researcher	University of Zagreb
12.	Miglena Nedeljković	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE
13.	IRENA MILER	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
14.	Ilda Zlatović	Student	PMF
15.	Franciska Pavić	Researcher	PLANTAR
16.	Franciska Pavić	Researcher	PLANTAR
17.	Jelena Križanović	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE
18.	Marko Križanović	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE
19.	Nikola Jukić	Researcher	University of Zagreb
20.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
21.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 1. 7. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/ researcher/ professor/other...)	Institution
22.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
23.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
24.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
25.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
26.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
27.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
28.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
29.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
30.	Marko Križanović	Researcher	BIOSENSE
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Figure 45. Attendee list, 1.7.2022.

A total of 79 interested participants registered for the event via the **NANOFACTS** webpage, comprising students, researchers, professors from outside the **NANOFACTS** consortium, and invited lecturers. In total, 52 participants attended the lectures on the first day of the **NANOFACTS** Training School related to cancer biosensing. The structure of participants was as follows: 23 students, 8 BIOS students, 26 researchers, 3 experts from partner institutions, 6 external experts, and 15 BIOS researchers.

During the second day, a total of 49 people attended the lectures. Of this number, 13 attendees were employed at BIOS, 25 were young scientists (junior researchers and students), and 24 were experienced researchers.

The third day was dedicated to learning about soft skills and problem-solving, with 46 participants, of which 13 were students and 33 were researchers (junior and senior).

Figure 46. Hands-on training session conducted by Eliana Manobianco and Francesco Floris on bio-chemical analyzer using imaging surface plasmon resonance, alongside a workshop led by Dr. Amelia Ultimo on in vitro assessment of therapeutic nanomaterials in both 2D and 3D cell cultures

Figure 47. Workshop lecture delivered by dr. Oliviero Gobbo on the topic of "Designing Animal Experiments"

In total, 33 attendees participated in a training session focusing on cancer biosensing, comprising 27 BIOS staff, 13 BIOS students, 14 BIOS senior researchers, 1 BIOS technician, and 2 TCD researchers. On the fifth day of the TS week, three workshop lectures (WSLs) focusing on Cancer Theranostic Nanomaterials were conducted. A total of 30 individuals attended these lectures. Among them, 23 were BIOS employees, 12 were young scientists (including junior researchers and students), and 18 were experienced researchers.

All attendees, invited speakers, and researchers who participated in lectures and workshops were given a certificate of appreciation (shown in Figure 47).

Figure 48. NANOFACTS Training School: Certificate of appreciation and Certificate for participation

Table 3: Overall statistics of NANOFACTS Training School attendees

	1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	4 th day	5 th day
students	17	16	13	2	2
researchers	32	36	33	31	28
lecturers	21 in summary				

2.3.2. Event attendance

The 23rd IEEE International Conference on Nanotechnology, IEEENano 2023

Staff involved: MSc Ivana Kundačina , MSc Aleksandra Pavlović, Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Palma de Mallorca, Spain

Date: 04 – 08 July 2022

Website: <https://2022.ieeenano.org/>

Goal: Presenting **NANOFACTS** research and networking in nanomaterial and nanosensors community

Brief report:

In Palma de Mallorca, Dr. Nikola Knežević delivered a presentation during the conference, contributing to the session focusing on nano-biomedicine. He was accompanied by Ivana Kundačina (ex Podunavac) and Aleksandra Pavlović, who actively participated in the event. Their presence facilitated extensive networking opportunities and provided comprehensive insights into diverse research endeavors within the realms of nanobiomedicine, nanosensors, and nanofabrication.

Picture:

Figure 49. NANOFACTS team at the IEEENano23 Conference

Science to Business Camp

Staff involved: MSc Mirjana Mundžić

Place: Congress Centre of SAS Smolenice, Slovakia

Date: 17 – 20 August 2022

Website: <https://inova.to/en/event/science-to-business-camp/>

Goal: Learn how to get science closer to business, how to commercialize research, bring it to public use and make profit.

Brief report:

Mirjana Mundžić, participated in “Science to Business Camp” in Smolenice Castle, Slovakia, organized by [INOVATO](#) Cluster. She attended and actively participated in more than 15 lectures and workshops organized on the topic of commercialization of scientific research. These events were prepared by 10 speakers who covered a wide range of topics, including preparing presentation of ideas and financial plans, intellectual property protection, selecting funding sources, and other relevant aspects. The most valuable insights were shared by Stephen Russo, author of the book "Science Commercialization," and Pavol Čekan, CEO of the innovative biotechnology company MultiplexDX, specializing in molecular biology, biochemistry, and oncology. Their success stories provided inspiration and practical insights into the process of commercializing scientific research.

Through these events, Mirjana gained knowledge and contacts that will be invaluable for her future projects and collaboration between science and industry. These experiences will enable her to more effectively develop and implement new ideas, as well as establish sustainable connections between the academic community and industry.

Pictures:

Figure 50. MSc Mirjana Mundžić at Science to Business Camp in Smolenice Castle, Slovakia

3rd EUROMBR training course

Staff involved: Alexandra Lorenz, Helene Stütz (master students)

Place: Faculty of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Date: 19 – 23 September 2022

Website: <http://www.eurombr.eu/>

Goal: The goal of this visit was to learn more about microfluidics and microreactors and to get hands-on training led by experts in the field.

Brief report:

The EUROMBR training course on innovative microreactor applications in bioprocess development was a 5-day training course with a lecture program and laboratory hands-on sessions covering the following topics: Microfabrication, microfluidics, sensors and inline-analytics, ultrahigh throughput screening based on droplet microfluidics, enzyme immobilization in microreactors, biocatalysis and cell culture in microreactors, modelling and design of processes in microfluidic systems. The master students received an extensive training in the field of microreactor fabrication.

Picture:

Figure 51. TUW NANOFACTS Members at University of Ljubljana

HYMA2022 (7th International Conference on Multifunctional, Hybrid and Nanomaterials)

Staff involved: Dr. Amelia Ultimo

Place: Genoa, Italy

Date: 19–22 October 2022

Website: <https://www.innomem.eu/event/7th-international-conference-on-multifunctional-hybrid-and-nanomaterials/>

Goal: Presenting research and establishing potential collaborations

Brief report:

Dr Amelia Ultimo attended HYMA2022 (7th International Conference on Multifunctional, Hybrid and Nanomaterials) In Genoa, Italy. This is a large, international, and interdisciplinary conference focused on hybrid materials where around 1000 researchers from all over the world shared their research through oral sessions and poster's presentations. Dr Ultimo presented the results obtained by the team on the development of a combination strategy (targeted cancer-derived exosomes and stimuli-responsive mesoporous silica nanoparticles) for the treatment of neuroblastoma and glioblastoma multiforme using 2D and 3D cultures.

Picture:

Figure 52. Dr Amelia Ultimo with Dr. Binh T. Mai at HYMA2022 Conference

15th International Scientific Conference "Students Encountering Science"

Staff involved: MSc Mila Đisalov, MSc Aleksandra Pavlović

Place: Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Date: 17 - 19 November 2022

Website: <https://stes.unibl.org/>

Goal: Presenting research and regional networking

Brief report:

MSc Mila Đisalov and MSc Aleksandra Pavlović, actively participated in the 15th International Scientific Conference "Students Encountering Science" held in Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina. The primary objective of the conference, known as StES, is to stimulate and cultivate the research endeavors of young scholars while fostering a culture of academic excellence. Through its platform, StES aims to promote the cultivation of scholarly inquiry among the youth. During the event, Mila Đisalov delivered an oral presentation elucidating her abstract titled "LAMP Primer Design for Monitoring Gene Expression of Tumor Markers in 3D Cancer Cultures." Likewise, Aleksandra Pavlović shared her research through an oral presentation titled "Nanosensor for Glutathione".

Picture:

Figure 53. MSc Mila Đisalov and MSc Aleksandra Pavlović at 15th International Scientific Conference "Students Encountering Science"

Open Science Communication 2022

Staff involved: MSc Stefan Jarić and MSc Aleksandra Pavlović

Place: Belgrade, Serbia

Date: 24 – 25 November 2022

Website: <https://stillinbelgrade.com/open-science-communication-conference-openscicomm-2022/>

Goal: Learning about the concept of Science Communication - public presenting science- related topics

Brief report: Open Science Communication 2022 was International Conference organized by Center for the Promotion of Science with an aim of strengthening the understanding of science and increasing scientific literacy as an indispensable part of everyday life. One of the main goals of this conference was to promote the concept of Science Communication as it refers to public presenting science-related topics not only among scientists but primarily targeting all social strata. Participation in the conference broadened the horizons and stimulated the critical thinking of researchers, and it also encouraged the development of new ideas in the presentation of scientific research data and results.

Picture:

Figure 54. MSc Aleksandra Pavlović and MSc Stefan Jarić at Open Science Communication Conference in Belgrade, Serbia

International Meet on Pharmaceuticals and Drug Delivery Systems (Pharmameet2023)

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Porto, Portugal

Date: 09 – 11 Februar 2023

Website: <https://10times.com/e12r-khzp-6p16>

Goal: Delivering keynote lecture and presenting latest **NANOFACTS** research

Brief report:

Dr. Nikola Knežević attended the International Meet on Pharmaceuticals and Drug Delivery Systems (Pharmameet2023), hosted in Porto, Portugal. As a distinguished participant, Dr. Knežević assumed the role of keynote speaker, delivering an address titled: "Cyclodextrin-Capped Mesoporous Silica-Based Nanomaterials for pH-Responsive Targeted Theranostics of Glioblastoma Multiforme". This lecture served to elucidate the significant advancements and applications of nanotechnology in the

realm of pharmaceuticals, particularly in the context of developing innovative and responsive therapies tailored for Glioblastoma Multiforme.

Picture:

Figure 55. Dr. Nikola Knežević at Pharmameet 2023 in Porto, Portugal

20th International Conference on Nanosciences & Nanotechnologies

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Thessaloniki, Greece

Date: 04 – 07 July 2023

Website: <https://rc.auth.gr/en/conference/151>

Goal: Presenting **NANOFACTS** research

Brief report:

Dr. Nikola Knežević was an active participant in the 20th International Conference on Nanosciences & Nanotechnologies, convened in Thessaloniki, Greece. Throughout the conference, Dr. Knežević delivered a comprehensive presentation, providing notable insights into the progress and advancements of the **NANOFACTS** project. Specifically, emphasis was placed on the ongoing development endeavors about theranostic nanoparticles designed for both the treatment and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) diagnostics of Glioblastoma Multiforme.

Picture:

Figure 56. PI Dr. Nikola Knežević presenting results in Thessaloniki, Greece

NETPORE 2nd International Training School

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Athens, Greece

Date: 17 - 20 July 2023

Website: <https://netpore.eu/TSAth/speakers.php?evt=14>

Goal: presenting **NANOFACTS** research

Brief report:

Dr. Nikola Knežević took stage as a keynote speaker at the NETPORE 2nd International Training School held from July 17 to 20, 2023, in Athens, Greece. This special event was hosted by the Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology at the National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos." During the gathering, Dr. Knežević shared insights into the use of tiny particles mesoporous silica and organosilica nanoparticles and their exciting potential in detecting glioblastoma cancer, treating it, and imaging. By speaking at this event, Dr. Knežević not only shed light on cutting-edge research but also encouraged collaboration among fellow researchers and students. This sharing of knowledge promises to advance our understanding of how nanotechnology can help in the fight against cancer.

Picture:

2nd International Training school, July 17-20, 2023 (Athens, Greece)

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles: functionalization, characterization and applications for cancer sensing, therapy and imaging

Dr. Nikola Knežević

Figure 57. Dr. Nikola Knežević, a keynote speaker at the NETPORE Conference in Athens, Greece

A three-day virtual Workshop held by Ratul Kumar Das, Ph.D.

Staff involved: Mirjana Mundžić

Place: online

Date: 09 – 11 August 2023

Website: <https://nanoschool.in/>

Goal: Workshop “Designing Nanoparticles for Targeted Cancer Therapy”

Brief report:

Mirjana Mundžić actively participated in a three-day virtual Workshop held by Ratul Kumar Das, Ph.D., specialized scientist in Nanobiotechnology, research consultant from Save The Environment, India.

The workshop covered a range of essential topics aimed at advancing the understanding of nanoparticle applications in cancer treatment. Sessions included an in-depth exploration of the fundamentals of nanoparticles, their unique properties, and their potential for targeted cancer therapy. Attendees delved into cancer biology basics to gain insights into the biology of cancer cells and its significance in crafting precise therapeutic strategies. Also, different methodologies for tailoring nanoparticles to specific cancer types and tumor microenvironments were discussed. Participants were engaged in insightful discussions on targeting mechanisms, exploring ligands and surface modifications that facilitate enhanced precision in targeting cancer cells. Nanoparticle imaging and tracking techniques were explored for their ability to visualize and monitor nanoparticles *in vivo* during cancer treatment. Moreover, the Workshop addressed the critical subject of nanotoxicology and safety considerations, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the safety and potential toxicity concerns associated with nanoparticle-based therapies.

Picture:

Figure 58. MSc Mirjana Mundžić at a three-day virtual Workshop

35th International Conference “Eurosensors 2023”

Staff involved: Stefan Jarić

Place: Lecce, Italy

Date: 10 - 13 September 2023

Website: <https://www.eurosensors2023.eu/>

Goal: Presentation of **NANOFACTS** research conducted during ESR visit to TUW

Brief report:

Stefan Jarić attended the 35th International Conference “Eurosensors 2023” held in Lecce, Italy, where he presented his latest research obtained during his visit to Vienna University of Technology (TUW) at Prof. Peter Ertl’s lab. The title of his oral presentation was “Electrochemical Detection of MMP-2 Using Graphene-Based Aptasensor”, which he presented during the session Biomedical sensors & diagnostics I. Also, the abstract is published in MDPI Proceedings (<https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2024097057>). Stefan's talk was dedicated to low-cost and simple technology for biosensor development, where the fully electrochemical approach was used to fabricate a reduced graphene oxide aptasensor and detect MMP2 in a PBS medium.

Picture:

Figure 59. MSc Stefan Jarić presenting research at EuroSensors 2023 in Lecce, Italy

NETPORE Webinar

Staff involved: Mirjana Mundžić

Place: online

Date: 21 September 2023

Website: <https://netpore.eu/WebinarSeptember21/index.php?evt=18>

Goal: Presenting **NANOFACTS** research

Brief report:

Mirjana Mundžić held a presentation titled “Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) for glioblastoma multiforme theranostics”. The presentation provided an overview of mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs), including their synthesis, functionalization, and characterization. Recent findings regarding the loading of MSN pores with dyes, drugs, and contrast agents were discussed, all aimed at achieving controlled drug delivery to specific targets, particularly within glioblastoma multiforme cells. Additionally, the potential utility of MSN for cancer diagnostics using MRI imaging was shown.

Picture:

Figure 60. MSc Mirjana Mundžić presenting “Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) for glioblastoma multiforme theranostics” at NETPORE Webinar

CoMBoS conference

Staff involved: MSc Mila Đisalov, MSc Teodora Knežić, MSc Marija Pavlović

Place: Belgrade, Serbia

Date: 6-8 October 2023.

Website: https://d1fdloi71mui9q.cloudfront.net/Vkir6LD8S4WcPnJDxjNF_CoMBoS-Drugo_obave%C5%A1tenje.pdf

Goal: Regional networking and gaining knowledge in the field of Molecular Biology

Brief report:

This Fall during the CoMBoS conference our ESRs Mila Đisalov and Teodora Knežić attended training session titled "iPSCs Spring School: iPSCs as a tool for modeling disease and discovering molecular mechanisms of NDDs" where they got to chance to learn about the use of iPSCs as cell models for cancer monitoring which is of great importance for our **NANOFACTS** research.

Understanding the potential of induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) in studying various diseases, including neurodegenerative disorders and cancer, is pivotal for advancements in medical research. These tiny powerhouses allow us to explore disease mechanisms and develop new therapies.

Picture:

Figure 61. MSc Mila Djisalov, MSc Teodora Knežić and MSc Marija Pavlović at CoMBoS Conference in Belgrade, Serbia

Workshop – Introduction to AI

Staff involved: MSc Silvia Schobesberger, MSc Alexandra Lorenz, MSc Sophie Schweinitzer, MSc Judith Krauß, MSc Konstanze Brandauer

Place: TU Wien

Date: 30 November 2023

Website: <https://femchem.chemie.tuwien.ac.at/index.php/introduction-to-ai-for-research/>

Goal: Introduction to Artificial Intelligence

Brief report: The primary objective of the workshop was to train attendees on utilizing various AI tools for research purposes. Throughout the session, several platforms were introduced and evaluated based on their capabilities. The critical discussion covered the use of AI in research, highlighting both its advantages and limitations. The workshop facilitated responsible usage of AI tools, empowering researchers to integrate these technologies into their work effectively. Overall, the session was instrumental in enhancing the attendees' proficiency with AI tools, ensuring they are well-prepared to apply these technologies in their research.

How to Communicate Modern Science?

Staff involved: MSc Minja Mladenović

Place: Belgrade, Serbia

Date: 12 – 14 December 2023

Website: <https://www.cpn.edu.rs/kurs-kako-komunicirati-savremenu-nauku/?script=cir>

Goal: Spreading knowledge about effective science communication in today's dynamic landscape

Brief report:

Our researcher, Minja Mladenović, attended first science communication conference, the groundbreaking "How to Communicate Modern Science?" course in Serbia. This innovative three-day interdisciplinary event, the first of its kind in Serbia, connected doctoral and master's students alongside young researchers across all scientific fields. Led by Dr. Darko Donevski, an astrophysicist and science communicator, the course explored essential topics like research planning, collaboration strategies, diverse scientific communication methods, science-media relations, and securing European grants. The course featured insightful discussions with prominent guests including Dr. Vernesa Smolčić, Dr. Ana Černok, Dušan Pavlović, Milica Ninković, and Ivan Umeljić. This immersive experience enriched Minja's understanding of effective science communication in today's dynamic landscape.

Picture:

Figure 62. MSc Minja Mladenović at "How to Communicate Modern Science?" course in Belgrade

Lecture on "Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Future Perspectives for Mapping Neurological Activity"

Staff involved: MSc Mirjana Mundžić

Place: Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade

Date: 08 April 2024

Website: N/A

Goal: Introduction to Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Future Perspectives for Mapping Neurological Activity

Brief report:

The lecture on “Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Future Perspectives for Mapping Neurological Activity” was given by dr Goran Angelovski, Senior Researcher from the Laboratory of Molecular and Cellular Neuroimaging at the International Center for Primate Brain Research, Center for Excellence in Brain Sciences and Intelligence Technologies (CEBSIT), Chinese Academy of Sciences in Shanghai, China.

Dr Angelovski's expertise lies in the field of neuroscience, with a focus on advanced brain imaging techniques and their applications. During the lecture, he provided insights into the latest developments in functional magnetic resonance imaging and its role in understanding neurological activity. He discussed recent research findings and methodologies employed by the Center for Excellence in Brain Sciences and Intelligence Technologies, Shanghai. The presentation highlighted the importance of international collaboration in advancing brain research which facilitates the exchange of knowledge and expertise, fostering innovation and progress in neuroscience and related fields.

Pictures:

Figure 63. MSc Mirjana Mundžić at lecture on “Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Future Perspectives for Mapping Neurological Activity” given by dr Goran Angelovski

8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević, MSc Stefan Jarić, MSc Ivana Milosević

Place: Seville, Spain

Date: 12-15 May, 2024

Website: <https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/all/international-conference-on-bio-sensing-technology>

Goal: Attending the 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology and poster presentation of the research partly supported by NANOFACTS

Brief report: Dr. Nikola Knežević, MSc Ivana Milosević and MSc Stefan Jarić attended the 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology, organized by Elsevier and held in Seville, Spain, from May 12-15. Dr. Knežević gave a talk entitled: "Novel Cost-effective Electrochemical Systems for Sensing Cancer Biomarkers.". This work, in its final stages, explores promising avenues for enhancing cancer detection through affordable electrochemical methods. Stefan presented his latest research obtained with the support of the NANOFACTS project through a poster presentation. The title of his presentation was “Low-cost approach for determination of NTproBNP in saliva using graphene-based aptasensor”, which he presented during the poster session 2. Stefan's poster elaborated on a low-cost

and simple technology for biosensor development based on reduced graphene oxide FETs, which was assembled in an aptasensor for the ultrasensitive determination of NTproBNP in artificial saliva as a real-sample model. The presentation was focused on the two-parameter analysis of the sensor signal development, explaining the physics behind the aptasensor working principle. MSc Ivana Milosevic presented paper entitled “Gold leaf electrochemical biosensor utilizing flagellar filament for sensitive Ni detection” in the poster session, related to the development of biosensors based on flagellar filaments.

Figure 64. Dr. Nikola Knežević presenting research at 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology, Seville, Spain

Figure 65. MSc. Stefan Jarić at 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology in Seville, Spain

4th International Electronic Conference on Biosensors (IECB 2024)

Staff involved: Dr Slavica Savić Ružić, MSc Stefan Jarić

Place: online

Date: 20 – 22 May 2024

Website: <https://sciforum.net/event/IECB2024?section=#program>

Goal: Attending the 4th International Electronic Conference on Biosensors

Brief report:

The 4th International Electronic Conference on Biosensors (IECB 2024) was held online from May 20-22, 2024. The conference successfully gathered global experts to share and exchange knowledge on the latest advancements and applications of biosensors. Presentations covered diverse topics such as environmental monitoring, disease detection, food safety, defense, and drug discovery. The event also focused on engaging young scientists, encouraging their active participation and contributions to the field.

Stefan Jarić participated in the conference with an abstract of his latest research obtained from the NANOFACTS project. The title of his abstract was “Utilizing the High Sensitivity toward MMP-2 of an Electrochemically Reduced Graphene Oxide Aptasensor” in a session F: Nanomaterials and Smart Surfaces in Biosensors. The application of an affordable and simple technology of highly sensitive and selective aptasensor for MMP-2 detection was proposed and used for human serum sampling. In a proof-of-concept approach, we showed promising results in the determination of MMP-2 in human serum samples comparable to standardized ELISA method.

Certificate of Participation

This certificate of attendance is given to

Slavica Savić Ružić

for participating at

The 4th International Electronic Conference on Biosensors
20-22 May 2024, online

iecb2024.sciforum.net

C. Gardini
Charlotte Gardini
Senior Conference Manager

Figure 66. Dr. Slavica Savić Ružić Certificate of Participation at IECB 2024

Certificate of Participation

This certificate of attendance is given to

Stefan Jarić

for participating at

The 4th International Electronic Conference on Biosensors
20-22 May 2024, online

iecb2024.sciforum.net

C. Gardini
Charlotta Gardini
Senior Conference Manager

Figure 67. MSc Stefan Jarić Certificate of Participation at IECB 2024

NANOSPAIN2024

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Taragosa, Spain

Date: 04 – 07 June 2024

Website: <https://www.nanospainconf.org/2024/index.php>

Goal: Presenting NANOFACTS research and networking

Brief report:

Dr. Knežević recently presented final research from the NANOFACTS project at the NANOSPAIN2024 conference held in Tarragona, Spain from June 4th to June 7th. His presentation delved into " Potential of MRI-based Sensing of Cargo Release from Mesoporous Silica for Tracking Drug Delivery Capabilities" presenting research published in the final stages of project. The conference brought together leading experts and researchers in the field of nanotechnology to explore the latest advancements and discoveries. It served as a platform for networking, collaboration, and fostering innovative solutions to pressing global challenges across various research areas.

Figure 68. Dr. Nikola Knežević at NANOSPAIN2024 Conference in Taragosa, Spain

9th European Congress on Advanced Nanotechnology and Nanomaterials

Staff involved: Dr Vasa Radonić

Place: Amsterdam, Nederland

Date: 24-25 June, 2024.

Website: <https://nanomaterialsconference.com/>

Goal: Participation at conference and workshop related to microfluidics development

Dr. Vasa Radonic took stage as a keynote speaker at the 9th International congress of biomaterials and biosensors BIOMATSEN 2024 held from April 18 to 24, 2024, in Olydeniz, Turkey presenting a talk entitled “Innovations in Gold Electrode Manufacturing for Cost-effective Biosensors”. During the gathering, Dr. Radonić shared research results in the field of biosensors development and propose a newly developed technology for the realization of low-cost biosensor platform with a potential in detecting different tumor biomarkers. By speaking at this event, Dr. Knežević not only shed light on cutting-edge research but also encouraged collaboration among fellow researchers and students. This sharing of knowledge promises to advance our understanding of how biosensors can help in the fight against cancer.

Picture

Figure 69. Dr Vasa Radonić at 9th European Congress on Advanced Nanotechnology and Nanomaterials conference